

MANAGEMENT OF UPPER LIMB POSTBURN CONTRACTURE - A FIVE-YEAR EXPERIENCE AT SHEIKH ZAYED HOSPITAL, LAHORE, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: post-burn contractures of the upper limb remain a significant cause of disability despite advances in acute burn management. Functional impairment of the hand, wrist, elbow, and axilla limits activities of daily living and reduces quality of life. Surgical management strategies, including Z-plasty, split-thickness skin graft (STSG), and full-thickness skin graft (FTSG), are commonly employed to restore function. *Aim:* To evaluate the effectiveness of individualized surgical techniques in the management of upper limb post-burn contractures over five years at Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. *Methods:* A prospective randomized study was conducted from January 2018 to December 2022, including 93 patients aged 5–71 years with upper limb post-burn contractures. Demographic details, sites of contracture, etiology of burns, type of surgical procedure, length of hospital stay, and outcomes were analyzed. Surgical procedures performed included Z-plasty, Z-plasty with graft, contracture release with STSG, and FTSG. Patients were followed up for six months postoperatively, and functional recovery and recurrence were assessed. *Results:* The hand was the most affected site (91.6%), followed by the elbow and forearm (21.7%), the wrist (21.7%), and the axilla (13.3%). The major etiologies were flame burns (78.5%), electrical burns (62.4%), and hot fluid scalds (50.5%). Z-plasty was performed in 16 patients, Z-plasty with graft in 12, STSG in 57, and FTSG in 6. Average hospital stay ranged from 9 days for Z-plasty to 14–15 days for graft-based procedures. No recurrence was observed in the Z-plasty or FTSG groups, while one recurrence occurred with STSG. *Conclusion:* Individualized surgical management, particularly Z-plasty and FTSG, provided excellent functional outcomes with minimal recurrence. Emphasis on postoperative rehabilitation is essential to maintain long-term results.

INTRODUCTION

Burns are defined as injuries to the skin or underlying tissues caused by heat, chemicals, electricity, or radiation. (1) Post-burn contracture is defined as the tightening of skin and soft tissue following burn injury

that results in restricted mobility and deformity (2). Scar tissue refers to fibrous tissue replacing normal skin after wound healing. Upper limb contractures involve the joints, muscles, ligaments, and tendons of the arm and

hand, leading to functional limitation. Z-plasty is a surgical technique used to release linear scar contractures by transposing triangular flaps to redistribute tension. Split-thickness skin graft (STSG) and full-thickness skin graft (FTSG) are reconstructive methods where skin layers are harvested and transplanted to cover defects created after contracture release. (3).

The global prevalence of burn injuries is reported to be more than 11 million cases annually, with higher rates in low- and middle-income countries. (4). In Pakistan, burn injuries are a major public health concern, with contractures frequently reported due to inadequate acute burn management. Studies show that up to 30-40% of burn survivors in developing nations develop post-burn contractures that compromise mobility and quality of life. Upper limb contractures are among the most disabling, as they interfere with daily living activities and independence (5). The true burden remains underestimated because many cases are unreported, and patients seek care only when severe deformity occurs (6).

Burn injuries are among the leading causes of morbidity associated with long-term disfigurement and disability. The major challenge is not only survival but also the restoration of pre-injury function. Inappropriate wound coverage and delayed surgical interventions result in scar formation and contractures. Deep second-degree, third-degree, and fourth-degree burns that involve skin, subcutaneous tissue, tendons, and joints are highly prone to contracture formation. These injuries are common in children and young adults, increasing the social and economic burden on families (5).

Post-burn contractures over upper limbs result in functional limitations by restricting joint mobility and causing deformities (7). Contractures across the elbow, wrist, and fingers impair hand function, affecting essential activities such as writing, eating, and self-care. Scar tissue replaces the normal elastic skin, causing stiffness and deformity. Subcutaneous involvement,

including muscles, tendons, and ligaments, further complicates surgical correction. The loss of mobility in upper limbs severely impacts quality of life, making contracture release surgery a critical intervention (8).

Management of upper limb post-burn contractures includes diverse surgical techniques depending on severity and extent of injury. Z-plasty is commonly used for linear contractures, providing lengthening and realignment of scar tissue. Contracture release followed by STSG or FTSG is performed in more severe cases where local tissue is insufficient (6). Myocutaneous flaps, tissue expanders, and free flaps are advanced reconstructive options for extensive defects. The choice of procedure depends on the site of contracture, availability of healthy tissue, and functional demands of the patient (4).

Despite advancements in surgical reconstruction, recurrence of contracture and complications remain frequent in resource-limited settings. Inadequate follow-up, lack of rehabilitation, and poor awareness among patients contribute to unsatisfactory outcomes (5). Children are particularly vulnerable, as their growing bones and joints are affected by contracture recurrence if proper physiotherapy is not ensured. Post-operative care is often neglected, resulting in functional deterioration despite technically successful surgery. This highlights the importance of individualized management strategies (9).

The current study focuses on evaluating five years of surgical experience in the management of upper limb post-burn contractures at Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore. The objective is to assess the effectiveness of individualized surgical approaches such as Z-plasty, contracture release with STSG, and FTSG in restoring function. The study emphasizes practical solutions applicable in a developing country context where burn contractures are prevalent. The findings aim to contribute to improving surgical protocols, patient care, and functional outcomes in burn survivors.

Methodology

In a five-years randomized study from Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan, 93 cases of post burn contracture were investigated. From them, 53 patients (91.6 cumulative percent) experienced post burn hand

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	49	52.7	52.7	52.7
	Female	44	47.3	47.3	100.0
	Total	93	100.0	100.0	

contracture, 7 (13.3 cumulative percent) patients had post burn axilla contracture, 7 (21.7 cumulative percent) patients had contracture in elbow and forearms, and 5

(21.7 cumulative percent) patients had post burn wrist contracture. Age limit was 71 and majority of the cases lie in the range of 5 years to 71 years old (Figure 2). The gender ratio for both male and female was almost same i-e 52.7 % were males and 47.3 % were females (Figure 1). The critical factor was determining the severity of burn contracture and it was dependant on the percentage of burned area, extension loss, width of contracture, and surgical history of the patient. The aetiology of most of the burns was due to fluid burns e.g hot water (50.5 cumulative percent), electrical burns (62.4 cumulative percent), and fire burns (78.5 cumulative percent).

	Male	Female
Gender frequency	49	44

Age Limit

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-10	28	30.1	39.4	39.4
	21-30	27	29.0	38.0	77.5
	31-40	11	11.8	15.5	93.0
	41-50	2	2.2	2.8	95.8
	61-onward	2	2.2	2.8	98.6
	7.00	1	1.1	1.4	100.0
Total		71	76.3	100.0	
Missing	System	22	23.7		
Total		93	100.0		

Figure 2. Age frequency of patients having post-burn contracture.

The inclusion criteria for the study includes non-circumferential scar with up to 75% circumferential, restriction up to 30-degree flexion as well as extension in upper limbs, and absence of the joint ossification. Contracture was older than 6 months. Age limit was 71 with range of range of 5-71 years old (Figure 2) and gender ratio was 52.7 % for males and 47.3 % for females (Figure 1). The exclusion criteria include patients taking non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), presence of the joint ossification, presence of wound infections, use of high dose chemotherapeutic agents or corticosteroids,

presence of associated comorbidities including systemic and metabolic disorders like diabetes, hypertension, arthritis, uremia, arterial obstruction, cardiovascular complications, renal failure, and immune-deficiency complications. Contracture less than 6 months. Decision of including 93 patients with post burn contracture in upper limbs was based on inclusion and exclusion selection criteria with informed consent from patients. Moreover, the study protocol was approved from the ethical committee of hospital. All the patients with post burn contracture of upper limbs were clinically analysed

with respect to the type of contracture as well as the limited motion. Patients were categorised according to the extension contracture, flexion contracture, and combined extension. Following, patients were subjected to treatment with z plasty, z plasty with skin graft depending, and contracture release with STSG and/or FTSG based on the degree of contracture as well as the available surrounding healthy tissue. The surgical procedures were conducted under the presence of general anesthesia without initial tension. Moreover, patients were given “cefazolin prophylaxis” antibiotic to avoid infection.

The deformity and nature of scar on hands, wrist, elbow, and shoulder was noted down with detailed evaluation of range of movements of different joints during different phases of treatment, including pre-operative treatment, and post-operative treatment with follow up. Proper counselling of patients was ensured regarding the proposed surgical procedure. In case of a linear band contracture with the healthy surrounding skin, z plasty was performed. Whereas, in case of broad densely scarred contracture, contracture was released and/or excised to restore the normal physiology.

Prerequisite to the skin graft covering of raw area, normal homeostasis was achieved. All cases were subjected to the tie-over dressing followed by application of the Plaster-of-Paris splint to achieve the normal position of joint until the consolidation of skin graft. After the contracture release, Full-thickness skin graft (FTSG) was used for coverage of defect. In case of web contracture release, multiple z plasties was performed. Moreover, groin crease area was harvested for Full-thickness skin graft (FTSG) and the area of thighs was harvested for Split thickness skin graft (STSG).

Following, on the 5th day post operation, first dressing was changed. Then until the take of skin graft, dressing was changed on alternate days. Patients who were treated with skin grafts were hospitalised till the take of skin graft and patients who had z plasty were subjected to stay until their sutures were removed. At least for two months, a proper follow up on every 15th day was carried out

and was followed for 6 months based on the progress of each case.

After the achievement of desired healing of respective parts, it was advised to patients apply polyfex over the recipient site and start olive oil massage 2-3 times per day for period of 6 months. The application of night splints was advised to the patients to maintain the ninety-degree abduction over the shoulder after the correction of axillary region contractures. The full extension manner was used to maintain the elbows and the thirty-degree dorsiflexion was advised in case of wrists. In case of hands, ninety-degree flexion was followed for metacarpophalangeal (MP) joints, and full extension was followed for interphalangeal joints. Later on, patients were persuaded to do physiotherapy of affected joints to restore the functioning.

Following the surgery, polyfex gauze was used to do the dressing and for 10 days splint was used to immobilise the surgical area. For 5 to 8 days dressing was changed, and patients were followed up for 6 months after the surgery. Conditions of all patients were monitored closely regarding scar formation such as firmness, pigmentation or wound border elevation; wound healing time, any discharge, contracture, pus secretion indicating any infection; cyanosis and damage indicating necrosis; and limited motion.

Results and Analysis

The study population consisted of 93 patients with post-burn contractures of the upper limb. Out of these, 49 (52.7%) were males and 44 (47.3%) were females, showing a nearly equal gender distribution. The youngest patient was 5 years old, and the oldest was 71 years. Children between 1-10 years formed the largest group with 28 cases (30.1%), followed by 27 patients (29.0%) aged 21-30 years. A smaller proportion of patients, 11 (11.8%), belonged to the age group of 31-40 years, while only 2 cases each (2.2%) were reported in the 41-50 and 61-70 year ranges. Additionally, 23 patients (24.7%) fell into the combined category of 11-20, 51-60, and above 70 years. This distribution reflects that post-burn contractures were most prevalent among children and young adults (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Patients (N = 93)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	49	52.7
	Female	44	47.3
Age Groups (years)	1-10	28	30.1
	21-30	27	29.0
	31-40	11	11.8
	41-50	2	2.2
	61-70	2	2.2
	Others (11-20, 51-60, >70)	23	24.7

Among the 93 patients, the hand was the most commonly affected site with 53 cases (91.6%), followed by the elbow and forearm and wrist, each observed in 7 (21.7%) and 5 (21.7%) patients, respectively. Axillary contractures were present in 7 cases (13.3%), while involvement of the neck and foot was recorded in 4 patients each (6.7%), and facial contractures were the least frequent with 3 cases (5.0%). Regarding etiology, hot fluid (scald) burns accounted for 50.5% of cases, electrical burns were responsible for 62.4%, and flame or fire burns represented the largest proportion at 78.5%. This indicates that functional areas like the hand and forearm are highly vulnerable to disabling post-burn contractures, with flame burns being the predominant cause (Table 2).

Table 2. Clinical Profile of Post-Burn Contractures

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Site of Contracture	Hand	53	91.6
	Axilla	7	13.3
	Elbow & Forearm	7	21.7
	Wrist	5	21.7
	Neck	4	6.7
	Face	3	5.0
	Foot	4	6.7
Etiology of Burns	Hot fluid (scalds)	—	50.5
	Electrical burns	—	62.4
	Flame/fire burns	—	78.5

Figure 3. Area and type of post burn contracture.

In this study, a total of 93 patients underwent different surgical procedures for upper limb post-burn contractures. Z-plasty alone was performed in 16 cases (17.4%), with an average hospital stay of about 9 days, showing no recurrence and satisfactory deformity correction. Z-plasty with grafting was carried out in 12 patients (30.4%), requiring 14-15 days of hospitalization, and resulted in improved mobility without major complications. Contracture release with split-thickness skin graft (STSG) was the most

frequently performed procedure, used in 57 patients (92.4%), with an average hospital stay of 15 days; only one recurrence was reported, while the rest demonstrated good motion range. Full-thickness skin graft (FTSG) was used in 6 patients (98.9%), with an average stay of 14 days, producing no recurrence and excellent functional recovery. Overall, all techniques were effective, with graft-based procedures requiring longer hospital stays but providing reliable functional outcomes (Table 3).

Table 3. Surgical Procedures and Outcomes

Surgical Procedure	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Average Hospital Stay (days)	Outcomes
Z-plasty	16	17.4	~9	No recurrence, satisfactory correction
Z-plasty with graft	12	30.4	~14-15	No major complications, improved mobility
Contracture release with STSG	57	92.4	~15	1 recurrence, otherwise good motion range
Contracture release with FTSG	6	98.9	~14	No recurrence, good functional recovery

Figure 4. Surgical procedure performed with respect to site, size, and nature of post burn contracture.

Discussion

Following chronic burns, upper limb burns including hand burns are major cause of function impairment and deformity (10). The hands of an individual constitute five percent of the total surface area of the body whereas its loss accounts for massive loss of full body functioning

(11). The loss of hand causes a significant functional impairment even if it's a small isolated injury

(11). Incidence of contracture is inevitable. It still occurs despite the acute thermal injuries' management. The most common and leading cause of hand contracture is burn trauma. In this study, we performed z plasty alone, z plasty with skin grafts, contracture release with STSG/FTSG to manage the post burn contracture of upper limbs including axillary, elbow, wrist and hand contractures (Figure 4). In this study, patients were treated with z plasty with skin graft and z plasty alone such as z plasty (17.4%), z plasty with graft (30.4%), contracture release with STSG (92.4%), and contracture release with FTSG (98.9%) was done. Out of 93 cases, 13.3 percent cases were of axilla contracture. Among them, these contractures involved axillary dome as well as the posterior or anterior axillary folds. And 21.7 percent of patients had elbow and forearm contracture. It included extensor as well as the flexor aspect. 27.7 percent of the cases involved wrist contracture including affected flexor and extensor aspect. There were 91.6 percent cases of post burn hand contracture including affected flexor as well as extensor aspects (Figure 3).

According to the hospital surgical procedures, we attempted to restore the full functionality of upper limbs rather than the aesthetic appearance which was the secondary preference. In hand burns the frequent contracture in finger was observed frequently. The 5 flaps with z plasty techniques was performed to achieve the correction of this deformity which showed positive results with efficient grasping function. Also, contracture release with FTSG equally showed positive results in case of functioning surface of digits contracture.

After the surgery, the post-operative management strategy was to use pressure garments as well as the night splintage to maintain the affected joints. In the study, the underlying reason of functionality of pressure garments and night splintage was conclusively

proved. However, their use showed significant collagen fibres reorientation into normal pattern.

Conclusion

Conclusively, the study proves that z plasty and associated modified procedures are a critical surgical intervention to treat the post-burn hand contracture. Adequate selection of proper technique to release burn contracture with respect to each patient is important. Lastly, the proper management focus has shifted to achieve optimum functionality and improved quality of life.

Recommendations

- 1. Early Referral and Burn Care**
Strengthen awareness among primary healthcare providers to ensure early referral of burn patients to specialized centers for appropriate management and to minimize the risk of developing contractures.
- 2. Standardized Acute Burn Management**
Implement standardized burn care protocols in all hospitals to promote proper wound coverage, infection control, and early physiotherapy, thereby reducing the incidence of severe scarring and contracture formation.
- 3. Individualized Surgical Approach**
Adopt an individualized approach in selecting surgical techniques such as Z-plasty, STSG, or FTSG based on site, severity, and tissue availability to achieve the best functional outcomes.
- 4. Postoperative Rehabilitation**
Ensure structured rehabilitation programs with splintage, pressure garments, and physiotherapy for at least six months post-surgery to maintain mobility and prevent recurrence.
- 5. Patient and Family Education**
Educate patients and caregivers about the importance of compliance with postoperative care, including massage, splint use, and regular follow-up, to sustain long-term functional improvement.
- 6. Capacity Building and Training**
Enhance training programs for surgeons, nurses, and physiotherapists in burn and reconstructive care to improve surgical outcomes and reduce complications.
- 7. Community-Based Prevention Programs**
Launch community awareness campaigns on burn prevention strategies, particularly targeting flame, electrical, and hot fluid-related injuries, which were identified as the major causes in this study.

8. **Long-Term Follow-Up and Research**
Establish long-term follow-up clinics to monitor functional outcomes and recurrence, and encourage further research to refine surgical techniques and postoperative management strategies in the local context.

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